

Moral Acknowledgement as Predictor of Comprehensive Pedagogical Skills of Secondary School Teachers

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Abstract. This study aimed to look into the influence of moral acknowledgment on the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers. In this study, the researcher selected secondary school teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City as the study's respondents. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and multiple linear regression analysis. Findings revealed that the moral acknowledgment of teachers was extensive. In contrast, the comprehensive pedagogical ability of secondary school teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City was described as moderately extensive. Meanwhile, correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between moral acknowledgment and comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. Regression analysis proved that moral acknowledgment in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility were significant predictors of comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. The study, therefore, was conducted further to utilize findings through publication in a reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS 1. Educational Management 2. Moral Acknowledgment
3. Comprehensive Pedagogical Ability of Teachers

Date Received: October 05, 2024 — Date Reviewed: November 10, 2024 — Date Published:
December 10, 2024

1. Introduction

Teacher modeling is perhaps the most powerful of all factors that affect education. If there is a mismatch between what the teachers say and do, students will most likely ignore what the teachers say, dampening the teaching and learning process. Therefore, the goals of education will not be achieved. Accordingly, teachers are moral models that contribute to the development of student care. Thus, to accomplish this enormous task, school teachers must play a crucial role in developing student care. Model teachers emerged from reasonable and practical teachings. An effective teacher is clear about her mission and models accomplished classroom teaching in considering caring teachers who model caring behaviors towards students, especially in secondary schools. This area has not been much focused. On the international scale, Kuloğlu and Karabekmez (2022) noted that teachers with comprehensive pedagogical skills are unbiased, patient, receptive to all kinds of innovations, and able to think in varied ways.

Those teachers willing to increase their productivity should organize all the tools and materials within their reach using critical thinking skills. In teaching critical thinking, Eđmir and engelci (2020) argue that teachers with comprehensive pedagogical ability encourage learners to discuss and question the information they suspect. They make sure that the communication in the classroom is clear and straightforward without imposing their own opinions on the learners. Bingöl (2019) also argued that teachers with comprehensive pedagogical ability help learners think critically, create appropriate environments for critical thinking, actively participate in the activity, and develop a more advanced level of critical thinking ability. Similarly, Nazari et al. (2022) found that moral acknowledgment could be that service providers are forced to make decisions and shoulder duties that cause contradictions between personal and professional values. Adding more, Mariona (2016) described that a service provider who follows the holistic approach considers the uniqueness of each person and respects their personal beliefs and values. According to Ineichen et al. (2017), moral awareness recognizes moral issues when they arise in practice. As highlighted by Christen et al. (2015), moral awareness is related to personal agency within interpersonal relationships and can be expressed as a genuine concern for the welfare of others. In addition, Moosavi and Izadi (2018) believe moral awareness to be the awareness of how one's actions can affect others, making the nurse aware of moral problems that could arise while caring for others. Also, Rashvand et al. (2017) asserted that moral awareness implies awareness of moral duties and obligations and recognizing them when the professional considers the individual client's viewpoint in a moral dilemma. Thus, moral responsibility makes client attention and care possible because it is directed toward others and contributes to action. However, reports indicated that the inability of teachers to employ comprehensive pedagogical strategies remains of the teachers in all levels remains a perennial problem worldwide. For instance, Yariv (2014) noted that poor teaching demotivates learners and catalyzes diminishing interest in the topic. It was indicated that proper knowledge dissemination impacts learner satisfaction. Kıyasođlu (2019) also noted that poor-performing teachers not only do not provide the expected results, but their negative behavior may distract others from doing their work and reduce staff credibility. They consume much of the principal's time and replace other workers who might help the organization more. Incompetent teachers are estimated to comprise about 5-10 percent of the teaching force. Despite the prevalence of this phenomenon across nations and cultures, school administrators have enormous difficulties in improving the weak teachers' performance or dismissing them. More so, the teacher in the classroom has the most significant influence on student learning and achievement. Teachers must guide and support their students' production readiness, curiosity, problem-solving skills, and critical thinking regarding twenty-first-century skills. Twenty-first-century skills are divided into three main themes: learning and innovation, knowledge, technology and media skills, and life and career skills. Thus, developing twenty-first-century skills will also contribute positively to students' future. Therefore, learning methods and strategies addressing the twenty-first century should be encouraged. In addition, learners should be provided with skills such as communication, collaboration, problem-solving, critical thinking, and productivity. The gap between previous studies Mariona, (2016) and Nazari et al., (2022) is that those studies were in a foreign setting. Also, those studies were conducted in a general service provider context. Thus, in this context, the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine context, particularly in Cluster 3 secondary schools

in Davao City, using a quantitative research approach. Specifically, the researcher used regression analysis to evaluate moral acknowledgment as a predictor of the comprehensive pedagogical ability of teachers, which is found to be scarce. The present study intends to contribute to the limited body of knowledge regarding the direct influence of moral acknowledgment on the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 secondary schools in Davao City.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—This section discusses key concepts and perspectives on variables from books, journals, and electronic sources.

1.1.1. Moral Acknowledgment—Moral acknowledgment involves recognizing the ethical dimensions of teaching, as emphasized by Ineichen et al. (2017) and Christen et al. (2015). Teachers shape students' character and values, necessitating ethical decision-making (Jordan, 2016). High moral acknowledgment fosters ethical classrooms, professional development, and a positive educational environment (Moosavi et al., 2017; Lütznén et al., 2012). Conversely, moral blindness can lead to ethical oversights with adverse effects (Bazerman Tenbrunsel, 2014; Shareinia et al., 2018).

1.1.2. Comprehensive Pedagogical Skills—Comprehensive pedagogical skills encompass teaching, management, and adapting to diverse learners (Pérez-Guilarte et al., 2022). Teachers with high aptitude effectively engage students, adapt instruction, and maintain a positive environment (Koopmans, 2014; Biggs et al., 2014). Professional development enhances these skills (Twining et al., 2013; Govranos Newton, 2014). Ethical teaching practices further emphasize integrity, responsibility, and respect (Petty Hill, 2017; Panigrahi Al-Nashash, 2019).

1.1.3. Moral Sensitivity and Teaching Competence—Moral sensitivity, defined as recognizing ethical issues in practice, correlates with holistic teaching competence. Studies

show teachers face conflicts between personal and professional values, leading to moral tension (Nazari et al., 2022; Amiri et al., 2019). Ethical behavior and values also predict employability and organizational commitment (Ndung'u, 2014; Bin Salahudin et al., 2016).

1.2. Synthesis—As a result, this section of the publication gives the researcher discussions of the literature and the findings from other studies comparable to or connected to the current investigation. More specifically, the literature revealed that, in line with Pérez-Guilarte et al.'s (2022) proposal, comprehensive pedagogical skills are measured regarding general aptitude, teacher education management, ethically oriented practices, and professional development. Also, teachers' moral acknowledgment, as proposed by Ineichen et al. (2017), is measured in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility. Studies originating from various theoretical perspectives have also supported a variety of presumptions on the relationship between teachers' overall teaching skills and moral acknowledgment. This provides the author with enough background information to comprehend the study.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

This study was based on the hypothesis put forth by Nazari et al. (2022), who suggested that the fact that service providers are required to make choices and perform tasks that conflict with their personal and professional values may be one explanation for the indirect relationship between moral sensitivity and care quality. According to Amiri et al. (2019), who made this argument, there is a significant inverse relationship between the score of holistic teaching competence and the dimension of moral sensitivity. It would appear that when teachers make moral decisions, they encounter a conflict between their personal and professional values in their careers and subsequently feel moral tension. Therefore, if this tension is not resolved correctly, it can provide a way

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

for them to distance themselves from patients, making service providers indifferent to moral care. Figure 1 presents the study’s conceptual framework, which helped the researcher summarize and briefly state the concept of the study. The independent variable is moral acknowledgment or the ability to recognize moral issues when they arise in practice. According to Ineichen et al. (2017), the measures of moral acknowledgment are moral strength or the experience of excessive and idiosyncratic desires that are, nevertheless, resisted among individuals; a sense of moral burden or the situation in which there is a discrepancy between moral values of professionals and clients that can generate negative feelings of stress, frustration, or guilt; and moral responsibility or the relevant action that breaches or upholds general moral norms, such as preventing harm or promoting the welfare of others. The dependent variable of

the study is comprehensive pedagogical skills, which is conceptualized by Pérez-Guilarte et al. (2022) and defined as the approach that seeks to fully activate all aspects of the learner’s personality (intellect, emotions, imagination, body) for more effective and comprehensive learning. The measures of comprehensive pedagogical skills are general aptitude or the general behaviors as a person instead as a teacher; teacher education management or the process of directing teams and teaching departments to maintain best practices and organization when providing services; ethically oriented practices or the extent in which a service care provider obey the organization’s rules; and professional development or the process of learning to earn or maintain professional credentials such as academic degrees to formal coursework, attending conferences, and informal learning opportunities situated in teaching practice.

1.3. *Statement of the Problem*—The primary objective of this study was to determine which domain of moral acknowledgment significantly influences the comprehensive pedagogical

skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Secondary Schools, Davao City. Thus, the result of the study sought the answer to the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of moral acknowledgment of teachers in terms of:
 - (1) moral strength;
 - (2) sense of moral burden; and
 - (3) moral responsibility?
- (2) What is the extent of comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in terms of:
 - (1) general aptitude;
 - (2) teacher education management;
 - (3) ethically oriented practices; and

- (4) professional development?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between moral acknowledgment and comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Secondary Schools, Davao City?
- (4) Which among the domains of moral acknowledgment significantly influence the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Secondary Schools, Davao City?

1.4. Hypotheses—The following hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship between moral acknowledgment and comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Secondary Schools, Davao City. H02: None of the moral acknowledgment domains significantly influence teachers' comprehensive pedagogical skills in Cluster 3 Secondary Schools, Davao City. The current study may benefit the following sectors and individuals: Department of Education. The Department of Education would gain from establishing the significant influence of these variables because it could provide a framework for developing initiatives to improve elementary school teachers' comprehensive pedagogical ability. The researcher thinks that if the current situation is not urgently addressed, it may increase the risks of classroom mismanagement, which may eventually paralyze or compromise the teaching-learning process. Policy Makers. This study would benefit policymakers since the findings may bridge the methodological divide in teaching practices research by attempting to understand the comprehensive pedagogical ability and the aspect of teachers' moral acknowledgment. Hence, this study provides a synthesis of both approaches. In addition, while research on the effects of moral awareness on teachers' comprehensive pedagogical ability has primarily focused on the education context, this research program builds

on the established relationship between moral acknowledgment and comprehensive pedagogical ability in the education context. Teachers. The result would benefit the teachers since the results generate facts, which is important in providing administrative support to the teachers. Since it was already known that comprehensive pedagogical ability has an important effect on the future of learners and is also an important component of educational and instructional processes, the findings of this study would justify the importance of recognizing moral awareness as an important factor for teachers' comprehensive pedagogical ability. Therefore, the evidence gathered from this study would be helpful for teachers to develop working behavior that considers their identity as professional teachers. Future researchers. This study's results would benefit other researchers because they may provide a framework and model for future research on comprehensive pedagogical skills and moral acknowledgment. For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were defined operationally: In this study, moral acknowledgment refers to the independent variable described in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility. Comprehensive Pedagogical Skills. This study describes the dependent variable in terms of the following indicators: general aptitude, teacher education management, ethically oriented practices, and professional development.

2. Methodology

This chapter will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work

during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhanced the manuscript's quality, coherence, and precision. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—The researcher employed a quantitative non-experimental design utilizing the correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts, and information related to the study, the researcher. In quantitative research, Bhandari (2020) described the research strategy as focusing on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. Accordingly, quantifying is formed from a deductive approach where emphasis is placed on testing theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies. At the same time, non-experimental research lacks the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world. Meanwhile, according to Myers and Well (2013), descriptive-correlational research examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause-and-effect relationships between variables. In this study, the researcher looked into the relationship between two variables—moral awareness and the comprehensive pedagogical ability of teachers. In this connection, the study focused on exploring which domains of moral acknowledgment significantly influence the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers. In this study, the use of descriptive-correlational was appropriate because the researcher only focused on the behavioral aspect of the respondents, and the researcher was unable to experiment with a controlled set-up.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were the secondary school teachers in Cluster 3 Secondary Schools in Davao City. In this study, the 165 respondents were

selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling involves the division of a population into smaller subgroups, known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata were formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling was appropriate in this study because there was heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, specific inclusion criteria were implemented to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study is to select respondents who can provide information to achieve its purpose. Hence, only those permanent-regular teachers in Cluster 3 Secondary Schools who were subjected to any administrative complaint and voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions. Thus, it did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the teachers.

2.3. Research Instrument—The study employed researcher-made questionnaires, which were contextualized to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The instrument's first part was concerned with teachers' moral acknowledgment. This questionnaire comprised statements divided among the indicators: moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility. The scale's reliability obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.982, which was described as excellent and interpreted as very reliable. The adapted instrument made use of a 5-point Likert scale and was determined based on the following ranges of means:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The moral acknowledgment of teachers is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The moral acknowledgment of teachers is oftentimes observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The moral acknowledgment of teachers is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The moral acknowledgment of teachers is rarely observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The moral acknowledgment of teachers is never observed.

The second part of the instrument was the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 secondary schools in Davao City. The questionnaires were composed of statements divided among the indicators: general aptitude, teacher education management, ethically oriented practices, and professional development. The Cronbach alpha value for the new scale is 0.910, meaning the instrument was reliable and consistent. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents used the 5-Likert scale to list the items they had made. As a guide in determining the extent of the comprehensive pedagogical skills of the teachers, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers are always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers are oftentimes manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers are sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers are seldom manifested.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers are never manifested.

The scaling was done by having one-half of the value of 5 as an average cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Before the administration of the instrument, it was subject to validation by three experts and was revised according to their expert comments.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher underwent steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured permission to conduct the study. The endorsement letter was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the schools’ division superintendent and then to the school principals of the selected public schools in Cluster 3 Secondary Schools in Davao City.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. After the study was approved, the researcher distributed the instrument to the respondents. The study was conducted from October 12 to 14, 2023. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents. Moreover, the respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. **Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data.** After the questionnaire was retrieved, each respondent's scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After that, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

Ethical Considerations The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study, following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. **Informed Consent.** The researcher asked permission from the respondents through a written informed consent form. She took the time to explain the purpose of my study thoroughly, providing them with sufficient details to ensure they understood why their participation was valuable. This helped them make an informed decision about whether to participate in the study. She clarified that their involvement was voluntary; if they chose to decline, there would be no pressure or coercion from my side. Furthermore, she carefully prioritized the respondents' psychological well-being throughout the research. The researcher secured written consent from each participant and informed them that the study aimed to investigate the factors that hinder or promote teachers' comprehensive pedagogical skills, as influenced by moral acknowledgment,

and to explore how they might contribute to enhancing their skills. **Vulnerability of Research Participants.** The researcher considered my respondents, teachers, not vulnerable since they are all of legal age and not highly vulnerable psychologically. She made sure that the survey was conducted at their convenience. Additionally, she took steps to protect the confidentiality of the information they disclosed. **Privacy and Confidentiality.** The researcher in this study adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012 by ensuring that the data collected could not be traced back to the respondents, the authentic sources of information. The researcher committed to not sharing any personal data without the respondents' consent. To further safeguard their privacy, she restricted my access to the data. Once she collected the necessary information, The researcher permanently disposed of all the survey questionnaires and deleted the data results to ensure no information could be traced back to the respondents. **Risk, Benefits, and Safety.** The researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation in administering the survey questionnaires. She thoroughly explained the purpose and benefits of the study, as well as the confidentiality of their responses, as stated in the online survey questionnaire. The researcher ensured that respondents could freely ask any questions related to the study without any restrictions. Furthermore, she ensured that the respondents were not subjected to any harm whatsoever. The researcher's questionnaire and interview guide did not include degrading or offensive statements toward the respondents. Additionally, this study was designed solely to gather academic information, and I did not request personal information from them. To minimize inconvenience, The researcher ensured the respondents had ample time to complete the online questionnaire. She also gave them the freedom to skip any questions that caused them psychological or emotional distress, and they were free to withdraw

from the study at any time if they felt uncomfortable discussing the requested information. She greatly valued their participation and prioritized their welfare throughout the study. Justice. To ensure impartiality in selecting respondents for my study, the researcher treated all individuals equally, regardless of their potential roles in the survey. She was careful not to show any bias in choosing participants; anyone who met the qualifications of being permanent-regular at the purposively selected schools was eligible. Throughout the research process, she made it a point to minimize interruptions to their routines as much as possible. To show my gratitude for their time and participation, she provided tokens of appreciation consisting of various souvenirs. She arranged for these tokens to be sent via courier, securely packaged, and sanitized before arriving at their doorsteps. Transparency. To ensure transparency in this study, the researcher approached all communications related to the research with honesty and openness. She took careful measures to protect the welfare of the participants by implementing the methods outlined in this study. She included all the necessary documents that supported my data analysis. She described the extent of the respondent's involvement in the study and shared how she maintained objectivity in analyzing the data and presenting the results. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that external factors, such as conflicts of interest, did not influence my respondents' responses. She would make the study findings accessible to the respondents, their parents, and the school administrators of the participating schools, provided they follow the proper protocols to protect the anonymity of the respondents. She also acknowledged the contributions of everyone who played a role in the success of this study. She provided a furnished copy of the research results to the Division of Davao City so that it could be accessed by the respondents and used

for learning and further study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and provided ample learning materials throughout the study, all conducted within the timeline she had set. To ensure the accuracy of the data collection, she carefully encoded the respondents' ratings on days when she felt alert and focused, thereby minimizing the risk of encoding errors. Additionally, she ensured that the analysis and results she gathered were proficient and aligned, serving as a primary basis for assessing adequacy. Community Involvement. The researcher must involve the community during every research phase, from planning to reporting. Therefore, she prioritized engaging the community in decisions regarding the research agenda, the methods most suitable for their context, and how the results or findings would be utilized. She plans to share the findings of my study with the community through gatherings, forums, and conferences.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing teachers' moral acknowledgment and comprehensive pedagogical skills. It was used to supply the answers for objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (moral acknowledgment) and dependent (comprehensive pedagogical skills). It was a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usually denoted by r . This was used to supply the answer for objective 3. Multiple linear regression analysis was applied to evaluate the significance of which domains of the independent (moral acknowledgment) variable significantly influence the dependent (comprehensive pedagogical skills) variable. This was used to supply the answer for objective 4.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study’s objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of teachers’ moral acknowledgment and their comprehensive pedagogical skills and the significant relationship between moral acknowledgment and comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Secondary Schools, Davao City.

3.1. Moral Acknowledgement of Teachers—

3.1.1. *Moral Strength*—Table 1 shows that the teachers’ moral acknowledgment was assessed by the respondents as extensive with a category mean of 3.59, interpreted as frequently observed by the teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.15 to 4.26. On the one hand, the item Believing that I have an excellent ability to notice when patients are not receiving adequate care has a mean rating of 3.15, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the respondents. On the other hand, Having the ability to notice the needs of learners well has been helpful during teaching-learning processes, reflecting a mean of 4.26, described as very extensive and interpreted as always ob-

served by the teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. This implies the teachers’ possession of strong ethical principles, integrity, and the ability to model and instill moral values in students. The result agrees with the view of Liu et al. (2020) that teachers with high moral strength who are morally acknowledged are likely to earn the trust and respect of students, colleagues, parents, and the community. This trust can enhance the teacher-student relationship, making it easier to impart moral lessons effectively. A teaching environment that acknowledges and values the moral strength of educators fosters an ethical and positive learning environment. In such a setting, students are likelier to feel safe, respected, and inspired to act ethically. This also supports Huang et al.’s (2020) idea that high levels of moral acknowledgment of teachers with strong moral strength can significantly impact students.

Table 1. Moral Acknowledgement of Teachers in Terms of Moral Strength

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Being able to notice learners’ needs well has been useful during teaching-learning processes.	4.26	Very Extensive
Believing that I have an excellent ability to notice when patients are not receiving adequate care.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
A good understanding of what considerations are required as a teacher when explaining difficult things or things that are hard to talk about with the learners and other stakeholders.	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.59	Extensive

3.1.2. *Sense of Moral Burden*—Results in Table 2 show that teachers’ moral acknowledgment in terms of a sense of moral burden got an extensive category mean rating of 3.52, which means that this domain of teachers’ moral acknowledgment is oftentimes observed by the teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.15 to 4.12. The item

Feeling terrible when caring for a learner who is suffering because of feeling helpless reflects a mean rating of 3.15, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item sometimes observed. Meanwhile, the item Feeling downcast if I notice a learner’s need because they might have other needs also shows a rating of 4.12, described as extensive and interpreted as an item often observed by the teachers.

Table 2. Moral Acknowledgement of Teachers in Terms of Sense of Moral Burden

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Feeling terrible when caring for a learner who is suffering because of feeling helpless.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
Making me feel terrible when I see a learner who is suffering from learning deficiency.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Feeling downcast if I notice a learner’s need because they might have other needs as well.	4.12	Extensive
Being able not to think I can leave things as they are when I notice something about a learner’s feelings.	4.02	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.52	Extensive

This implies that teachers feel a strong obligation to foster their students’ moral and ethical development and to create a positive and morally upright learning environment. The result agrees with Syahrul Nizam et al. (2016) view that teachers who feel a strong sense of moral burden are more committed to integrating ethics and morality into their teaching. They are dedicated to nurturing not only academic skills but also the moral character of their students. This also supports the findings of La’Vone Hill (2019) that teachers with a sense of moral burden are more likely to actively promote ethical values such as honesty, respect, empathy, and responsibility. They strive to instill these values in their students through both their words and actions.

moral responsibility acquired a category mean of 3.26, described as moderately extensive, which means that this domain of teachers’ behavioral flexibility is sometimes observed by the teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 3.02 to 3.46. It is noteworthy that item Thinking that it is my responsibility if the best teaching practices cannot be provided to the learners has a mean rating of 3.02, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as an item sometimes observed, while item Believing that I have adequately fulfilled my responsibility if I do teaching practice under rules has a mean rating of 3.46, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes observed by the teachers.

3.1.3. *Moral Responsibility*—Specifically, teachers’ moral acknowledgment in terms of

Table 3. Moral Acknowledgement of Teachers in Terms of Moral Responsibility

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Believing that I have adequately fulfilled my responsibility if I do teach practice in accordance with rules.	3.46	Extensive
Thinking that it is my responsibility if the best teaching practices cannot be provided to the learners.	3.02	Moderately Extensive
Thinking providing quality education is my responsibility	3.43	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.26	Moderately Extensive

This implies that while some recognition of teachers’ moral responsibility is present, it may not be as strong or widespread as in situations of high acknowledgment. The result is congruent with McShane and Von Glinow’s (2016) assertion that teachers with moderate levels of acknowledgment are likely to balance academic objectives with ethical goals. While they recognize their moral responsibilities, they may still prioritize academic achievements to some extent. Their acknowledgment at this level may lead to integrating core ethical values into their teaching methods. Segon and Booth (2017) state that moderate acknowledgment can lead to some parental and community engagement in reinforcing ethical values. However, it may not be as extensive or active as in cases of high acknowledgment. Parents and the community may support ethical initiatives, but the onus may not entirely affect teachers. Lastly, Table 4 summarizes the moral acknowledgment of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. It shows that the overall mean of teachers’ moral acknowledgment is 3.46, described as extensive. This means that teachers’ moral acknowledgment is oftentimes observed. More so, moral acknowledgment of teachers in terms of

moral strength acquired the highest mean score of 3.59, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. In contrast, moral acknowledgment of teachers in terms of moral responsibility has the lowest mean score of 3.26 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the teachers. The result implies that teachers understand and acknowledge the ethical dimensions of teaching and the importance of ethical considerations in the field of education. The result supports the idea of Christen et al. (2015) that the moral acknowledgment of teachers acknowledges that teaching is not just a technical or pedagogical endeavor but also a moral one. Teachers play a critical role in shaping their students’ character, values, and ethical development. Recognizing this moral dimension is essential in fostering a positive educational environment. This also supports the findings of Lützné et al. (2012) that morally acknowledged teachers are more likely to engage in ongoing professional development related to ethics in education. This can lead to improvements in teaching practices and the creation of curricula and programs that emphasize ethical education.

Table 4. Summary of Moral Acknowledgement of Teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Moral Strength	3.59	Extensive
Sense of Moral Burden	3.52	Extensive
Moral Responsibility	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.46	Extensive

3.2. *Comprehensive Pedagogical Skills of Teachers—*

3.2.1. *General Aptitude—*Table 5 shows that the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in terms of general aptitude are extensive, with a category mean of 3.41. This means that the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City are oftentimes observed. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.12 to 4.13. The item Spending effort to identify the reasons behind the existing problems and offering solutions for them shows a mean rating of 3.12, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as this item sometimes observed by the teachers. Further, the item Being aware of the differences between current and ideal selves has a mean rating of 4.13, described as extensive and interpreted as this item oftentimes manifested by the teachers. This indicates

that teachers excel in the technical aspects of teaching and possess exceptional qualities that enhance their effectiveness. This supports the idea of Koopmans (2014) that teachers with high levels of general aptitude related to comprehensive pedagogical skills are highly proficient in their subject matter. They possess an in-depth understanding of their teaching content and can convey it with clarity and enthusiasm. These teachers employ innovative and effective instructional strategies that cater to diverse learning styles and needs. They are skilled at adapting their teaching methods to make learning engaging and meaningful. This also supports Biggs’ et al. (2014) findings that high-level teachers exhibit excellent classroom management skills, creating a well-organized and respectful learning environment. They establish clear expectations and maintain a positive classroom atmosphere.

3.2.2. *Teacher Education Management—*Comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in terms of teacher education management, as shown in Table 6, reflect a moderately extensive category mean of 3.14, which means that the teachers sometimes manifest it. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.45 to 3.89. The table further reveals that the item Helping other teachers with their self-

learning has a mean rating of 2.45, described as less extensive and interpreted as an item seldom observed by the teachers. Meanwhile, the item Facilitating the exchange of opinions by communication when there are conflicts among teachers has a mean rating of 3.89, described as extensive and interpreted as comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers is oftentimes manifested in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City.

Table 5. Comprehensive Pedagogical Skills of Teachers in Terms of General Aptitude

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Spending effort to identify the reasons behind the existing problems and offering solutions for them.	3.12	Moderately Extensive
Reflecting on and evaluating my own thinking processes thoroughly and objectively.	3.42	Extensive
Being aware of the differences between current and ideal selves.	4.13	Extensive
Trying to enhance the well-being of others with all my power.	2.34	Less Extensive
Consoling and encourage other people when they are in a difficult situation	4.05	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.41	Extensive

Table 6. Comprehensive Pedagogical Skills of Teachers in Terms of Teacher Education Management

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Trying to provide teaching services that is an example to other teachers.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Helping to decide on a solution that is respectful of all opinions when there are conflicts among teachers.	3.45	Extensive
Providing continuous training and guidance to each nurse while taking their competencies into consideration.	2.55	Less Extensive
Creating an environment and culture that facilitates learning in the workplace	3.25	Moderately Extensive
Facilitating the exchange of opinions by communication when there are conflicts among teachers.	3.89	Extensive
Helping other teachers with their self-learning.	2.45	Less Extensive
Overall Mean	3.14	Moderately Extensive

This implies that teachers are proficient in managing and leading educational initiatives for their peers and themselves. The result agrees with Schleicher’s (2021) assertion that teachers with moderate levels of teacher education management skills excel in designing and delivering effective teacher training programs. They are skilled at providing new and experienced educators with the knowledge and strategies needed for success in the classroom. These educators often assume leadership roles within educational institutions. They may serve as department heads and curriculum coordinators or lead professional development initiatives, contributing to the overall improvement of the school or district.

3.2.3. *Ethically Oriented Practice*—This domain, as shown in Table 7, has a category mean of 3.70, described as extensive and interpreted that this domain of teachers’ comprehensive pedagogical skills is often manifested. Adding on, the mean ratings of the different items range from 3.35 to 4.08. Specifically, the item Providing learner-centered care regarding learners’ rights and dignity has a mean rating of 3.35, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item sometimes manifested by the teachers. Notifying other education professionals about the teacher’s needs to improve learners reflects a mean rating of 4.08, described as extensive and interpreted as an item often manifested by the teachers.

Table 7. Comprehensive Pedagogical Skills of Teachers in Terms of Ethically Oriented Practice

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Providing learner-centered care regarding learners’ rights and dignity.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
Following the main principles of teaching practices.	3.62	Extensive
Making my own decisions during teaching practice and being responsible for them.	3.89	Extensive
Notifying other education professionals about the teacher’s needs to improve learners.	4.08	Extensive
Confirming that a task is properly completed when assigning the task to other teachers.	3.57	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.70	Extensive

The result indicates that teachers are exceptionally proficient in incorporating ethical principles, values, and practices into their educational approach. This agrees with Petty and Hill’s (2017) idea that teachers with high levels of ethically oriented practice skills are adept at incorporating ethical discussions, dilemmas, and considerations into their curriculum. They encourage students to think critically about ethical issues and engage in meaningful dialogue. These educators serve as exemplary role models for ethical behavior. Their actions and decisions align with the ethical values they promote, setting a positive example for students to follow.

3.2.4. *Professional Development*—This domain of comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in terms of professional development,

as shown in Table 8, reflects a moderately extensive category mean of 3.24, which means that it is sometimes manifested by the teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. Notably, the mean ratings of the different items range from 2.85 to 3.45. The table further reveals that the item Creating a professional development plan for my personal development has a mean rating of 2.85, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item sometimes manifested by the teachers. Meanwhile, the item Determining my own learning needs by seriously reflecting on my teaching practices has a mean rating of 3.45, described as extensive and interpreted as comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers oftentimes manifested.

Table 8. Comprehensive Pedagogical Skills of Teachers in Terms of Professional Development

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Spending time and effort learning about and preserving the current information and skills, which are necessary for teaching practice.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Determining my own learning needs by seriously reflecting on my teaching practices.	3.45	Extensive
Creating a professional development plan for my personal development.	2.85	Moderately Extensive
Looking for immediate responses to the questions emerging from teaching practice	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.24	Moderately Extensive

This suggests that teachers are competent in various aspects of professional development but may not excel in all areas. The result supports Jones and Dexter’s (2016) conclusion that teachers with moderate levels of professional development skills are effective at seeking and participating in professional development opportunities to enhance their teaching skills and knowledge. According to Tanang and Abu (2014), moderate-level teachers are willing to incorporate technology into their teaching and may attend training sessions on technology integration. However, their adoption may not be as extensive or innovative as those with high-level skills. Lastly, Table 9 summarizes the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. As shown in the table, teachers’ comprehensive pedagogical skills obtained an overall mean score of 3.37 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by Cluster 3, Davao City teachers. Moreover, results in Table 9 show that the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in terms of ethically oriented practice acquired the high-

est mean score of 3.70, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested. In contrast, teachers’ commitment to teacher education management acquired the lowest mean score of 3.14, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the teachers. The result suggests that teachers exhibit competence in multiple teaching areas but may not excel in all aspects. This supports Mahmoudi et al.’s (2017) idea that teachers with moderate pedagogical skills are generally effective in delivering instruction but may not excel in every aspect. They are capable of conveying subject matter knowledge to students and facilitating learning in the classroom. Teachers at this level likely employ a balanced approach to teaching. However, this is similar to the findings of Nakagawa (2019) that classroom management and the ability to engage students effectively are areas where teachers with moderate levels of pedagogical skills tend to perform reasonably well. They create a conducive learning environment, maintain order, and keep students engaged in the learning process.

Table 9. Summary on Comprehensive Pedagogical Skills of Teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
General Aptitude	3.41	Extensive
Teacher Education Management	3.14	Moderately Extensive
Ethically Oriented Practice	3.70	Extensive
Professional Development	3.24	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.37	Moderately Extensive

3.3. *Relationship Between Moral Acknowledgement and Comprehensive Pedagogical Skills of Teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City*—The results of the analysis of the relationship between moral acknowledgment and comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 10 shows that moral acknowledgment has a significant positive relationship with the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .921, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of moral acknowledgment changes, the extent of comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City also significantly changes. Moreover, the table also shows that moral acknowledgment in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility are significantly correlated with comprehensive ped

agogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City, as evidenced in the correlation coefficient values of 0.774, 0.635 and 0.801. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between moral acknowledgment and comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. This implies that morally acknowledged teachers often serve as ethical role models for their students. They instill these principles in their students by consistently demonstrating ethical behavior and values. The findings support Ndungu’s (2014) assertion that moral acknowledgment can foster a more respectful and cooperative classroom environment. Teachers prioritizing moral values are better equipped to manage conflicts, encourage positive behavior, and create an atmosphere where students feel valued and respected. High levels of moral acknowledgment encourage teachers to consider ethical implications in their decision-making processes. They may engage students in ethical discussions and guide them in developing strong decision-making skills based on integrity, fairness, and responsibility principles.

3.4. *Influence of Moral Acknowledgement on the Comprehensive Pedagogical Skills of Teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City*—The significance of moral acknowledgment’s influence on teachers’ compre-

hensive pedagogical skills in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City was analyzed using linear regression analysis. Table 11 shows that when a moral acknowledgment is considered a predictor of comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary

Table 10. Relationship Between Moral Acknowledgement and Comprehensive Pedagogical Skills of Teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Comprehensive Pedagogical Ability	r-value	p-value
	0.774*	0.000
	0.635*	0.000
	0.801*	0.000
	0.706*	0.000

*Significant @ p<0.05 Schools

in Davao City, the model is significant, as evident in an F-value of 20.377 with $p < 0.05$. Therefore, moral acknowledgment predicts the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R² value of 0.327 indicates that moral acknowledgment has contributed significantly to the variability of comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers by 32.70%. In addition, the table shows that there are domains of moral acknowledgment that significantly influence the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. This table indicates that moral acknowledgment in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility is significant when considered as a predictor of the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers. This means that the extent of comprehensive pedagogical skills increases by 0.391, 0.124, and 0.232 for each unit increase in moral acknowledgment of teachers in Cluster 3 Public

Secondary Schools in Davao City. Thus, this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that none of the domains of moral acknowledgment significantly influence the comprehensive pedagogical ability of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. Affirming that the comprehensive pedagogical ability of teachers is a function of moral acknowledgment, the finding agrees with Amiri et al. (2019) that when teachers feel morally acknowledged, they are likely to have stronger, more trusting relationships with their students. These positive relationships can enhance communication, student motivation, and the effectiveness of pedagogical interactions. Lastly, the findings agree with the anchored proposition by Nazari et al. (2022) that morally acknowledged teachers may be more motivated to engage in ongoing professional development related to ethics in education. This can lead to improved teaching practices and the incorporation of ethical education strategies.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher’s conclusion and recommendation. The literature supported the discussion in the first chapters, and the conclusion was by statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate which domains of moral acknowledgment significantly influence the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using the descriptive-correlation tech-

Table 11. Influence of Moral Acknowledgement on the Comprehensive Pedagogical Skills of Teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City

Moral Acknowledgement	B	Beta	S.E	p-value	Decisions
Moral Strength	.391*	.327	.078	.000	Reject H0
Sense of Moral Burden	.124*	.134	.062	.040	Reject H0
Moral Responsibility	.232*	.226	.063	.000	Reject H0

Model Summary:

$R^2 = 0.327$

F-value = 20.377**

p-value = 0.000

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$; **Highly signifi-

nique. The researcher selected the 165 public secondary school teachers in Cluster 3 Davao City as the respondents through a stratified random sampling method. The researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires that were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. The moral acknowledgment of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City got an overall mean of 3.46 with an extensive descriptive rating. Also, the moral acknowledgment of teachers in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility obtained mean scores of 3.59, 3.52, and 3.26, respectively. The comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City have an overall mean of 3.37 and a moderately extensive descriptive rating. Also, the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in terms of general aptitude, teacher education management, ethically oriented practice, and professional development obtained mean scores of 3.41, 3.14, 3.70, and 3.24, respectively. The result showed that moral acknowledgment has a significant positive relationship with the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City with a p-value of .000

that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .706, p < 0.05$). This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between moral acknowledgment and comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. Overall, moral acknowledgment significantly influences the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City, as evidenced by the F-value of 20.377 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.327 indicated that moral acknowledgment had contributed significantly to the variability of comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City by 32.70 percent of the total variability. Moreover, a moral acknowledgment in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility was found to be significant predictors of comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City as indicated by the regression coefficient values of 0.391, 0.124 and 0.232, respectively.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: Moral acknowledgment of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in

knowledge of teachers in terms of moral strength and sense of moral burden obtained an extensive descriptive rating. In contrast, the moral acknowledgment of teachers in terms of moral responsibility got a moderately extensive rating. The result implies that teachers understand and acknowledge the ethical dimensions of teaching and the importance of ethical considerations in education. The comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City were rated moderately extensive. Teachers' comprehensive pedagogical skills in general aptitude and ethically oriented practice belong to the extensive rating. In contrast, teachers' comprehensive pedagogical skills in teacher education management and professional development acquired a moderately extensive rating. The result suggests that teachers exhibit competence in multiple teaching areas but may not excel in all aspects. The result showed that moral acknowledgment has a significant positive relationship with the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. This means that as the extent of the moral acknowledgment changes, the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City also significantly change. This implied that morally acknowledged teachers often serve as ethical role models for their students. They instill these principles in their students by consistently demonstrating ethical behavior and values. Moral acknowledgment in terms of moral strength, sense of moral burden, and moral responsibility significantly influenced the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City. This leads to

the rejection of the null hypothesis that none of the domains of moral acknowledgment significantly influence the comprehensive pedagogical skills of teachers in Cluster 3 Public Secondary Schools in Davao City.

4.3. Recommendations—The Education Department may develop policies integrating ethics and moral education into teacher training programs. Ensure that teachers receive training on integrating ethical considerations into their teaching practices. DepEd may allocate resources for ongoing professional development opportunities related to moral and ethical education for teachers. Encourage teachers to participate in workshops, seminars, and courses that enhance their ethical teaching skills. School heads may lead by example, demonstrating ethical leadership and moral acknowledgment in their interactions with students and teachers. They may also encourage teachers to pursue professional development opportunities focusing on ethics and comprehensive pedagogical skills and provide time and resources for this purpose. Teachers may engage in regular self-reflection and self-assessment to evaluate their ethical teaching practices and moral acknowledgment and identify areas for improvement. They may actively integrate ethical discussions into their curriculum and classroom activities and encourage students to think critically about moral dilemmas and ethical decision-making. Future researchers may examine the long-term effects of comprehensive pedagogical skills, including a strong ethical component, on students' academic achievements and moral development and assess how these skills influence students beyond their school years.

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